

Base-catalyzed reaction of acetohydroxamic acid in micellar media containing β -cyclodextrin[†]

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The kinetics of the base-catalyzed hydrolysis of acetohydroxamic acid (CH_3CONHOH) have been studied in media containing sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) or tetradecyltrimethylammonium bromide (TTAB) micelles and β -cyclodextrin (β -CD). The presence of β -CD inhibits the hydrolysis. Both β -CD-SDS and β -CD-TTAB systems exhibit inhibitory and catalytic effects. This behavior is explained in terms of two simultaneous processes, i.e. complexation/micellization. The CMC both in the absence and in the presence of β -CD have been determined conductometrically. These data indicate that the association process between the β -CD and surfactant has higher affinity than the micellization process.

Recently, several biologically relevant hydrolysis reactions have been studied in cyclodextrins¹. But there have been little research^{2,3} either on how cyclodextrins affect the properties of the micelles or on how the presence of micelles affects the behavior of cyclodextrin mediated reactions. Moreover, there appears no study dealing with cyclodextrin-mediated reactions of hydroxamic acids. Hydroxamic acids are important bioligands⁴. Since acetohydroxamic acids (AHA) are utilized as a drug for hepatic coma and a DNA scission agent⁵, we considered it interesting to study the effect of β -cyclodextrin and surfactants on the hydrolysis.

Results and Discussion

At constant $[\text{OH}^-]$ (0.04 mol dm^{-3}), the base-catalyzed hydrolysis of AHA was inhibited by the addition of β -CD (Table 1) and show a saturation effect (Fig. 1). Since the alkaline hydrolysis of hydroxamic acid is a very slow

reaction⁶, the reaction was carried out at 75° . In all the cases, pseudo-first order conditions were maintained. The observed inhibition of the hydrolysis reaction by the β -CD is due to the formation of an inclusion complex between β -CD and AHA, since the negative charge on the dissociated β -CD ($\text{p}K_a$ of β -CD = 12.2)⁷ will repel OH^- ions, complexed AHA will be unreactive. The mechanistic route is shown in Scheme 1.

Table 1. Pseudo-first order rate constant for the alkaline hydrolysis of AHA in the presence of β -CD

$10^3 [\beta\text{-CD}]$ mol dm^{-3}	$10^5 k_{\psi} (\text{s}^{-1})$
Nil	4.99
1.32	3.39
2.50	3.10
4.40	2.95
8.81	2.19
13.2	1.75
17.6	1.42
22.0	1.46

Fig. 1. (■) Influence of β -CD on the pseudo-first order rate constants of the alkaline hydrolysis of AHA; (◆) plot between $[\beta\text{-CD}]$ and $1/k_{\text{obs}}$.

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Based on this scheme the observed rate constant is

$$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_w[\text{OH}^-]}{(1+K_a[\text{CD}])} \quad (1)$$

where K_a is the association equilibrium constant and k_w the second order rate constant obtained in water ($1.24 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$). Eqn. (1) can be rearranged to

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k_w[\text{OH}^-]} + \frac{K_a[\text{CD}]}{k_w[\text{OH}^-]} \quad (2)$$

A plot according to eqn. (2) is linear (Fig. 1) and from the ratio of the slope and intercept the value of K_a ($=136 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3$) can be calculated. The good fit between eqn. (2) and the experimental results (Fig. 1) shows the validity of Scheme 1. Similar observations were also obtained for the basic hydrolysis of *N*-methyl-*N*-nitroso-*p*-tolunesulfonamide in media containing β -cyclodextrins³.

Reaction in the presence of β -CD/SDS mixtures : The rate constants for the base-catalyzed hydrolysis of AHA in the absence of β -CD increases with varying concentration of SDS. In this work, the influence of SDS concentration on k_{obs} was determined at fixed concentration of β -CD ($= 8.81 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$). The results are given in Table 2. The rate constant increasing with [SDS] tends to maxima, and further increase in [SDS] leads to a slow decrease in the observed rate. This behavior can be explained qualitatively considering the two simultaneous processes, i.e. complexation and micellization. Before addition of SDS, AHA and β -CD form inclusion complex. This association decreases the reactive AHA concentration in aqueous medium. When SDS is added to the reaction mixture the rate increases first and then decreases. Addition of SDS to medium produces complexation of surfactant monomers with β -CD (SDS- β -

CD) with displacement of AHA to the aqueous medium, thereby increasing reactive [AHA]. At higher concentration of SDS, a competition between the two processes (complexation/micellization) is established. As it is anionic micelles, simple electrostatic consideration excludes the presence of OH^- at the micellar surface. The effect of AHA association of micelle is reflected as a decreasing concentration of reactive AHA and consequently slower reaction rate.

Reactions in the presence of β -CD/TTAB mixtures : The results given in Table 3 show the effect of TTAB in the

Table 3. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the alkaline hydrolysis of AHA in β -CD/TTAB mixtures

Temp = 75°, [NaOH] = 0.04 mol dm⁻³

10 ³ [TTAB] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k _ψ (s ⁻¹)	
	[β-CD] = Nil	[β-CD] = 8.81 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³
Nil	4.99	2.19
4.46	3.45	1.70
14.9	4.25	2.04
29.7	-	2.73
44.6	5.32	3.77
59.4	-	3.05

Table 2. Pseudo-first order rate constants for the alkaline hydrolysis of AHA in β -CD/SDS mixtures

Temp = 75°, [NaOH] = 0.04 mol dm⁻³

10 ³ [SDS] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ k _ψ (s ⁻¹)	
	[β-CD] = Nil	[β-CD] = 8.81 × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³
Nil	4.99	2.19
0.87	5.20	-
2.60	5.67	-
3.47	-	2.43
8.67	4.94	2.78
17.3	4.43	3.17
34.7	-	3.96
52.0	4.29	3.24

presence of constant [β-CD] ($= 8.81 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) on the alkaline hydrolysis of AHA. The observed first order rate constant increases rapidly with [TTAB], goes through a maximum and decreases gradually thereafter. This behavior can be explained by considering the pseudo-phase ion exchange model, with micelles and water regarded as distinct reaction regions⁸. Firstly the TTAB monomer complexation with β -CD expels AHA from the AHA-CD complex, transforming it into reactive AHA. At higher concentration of TTAB (after micellization), AHA will be distributed between the aqueous and micellar pseudo-phase. In this case, as it is a cationic micelle, OH^- will be present at the micellar surface. The TTAB micelles help in bringing the reactants in the Stern layer and reaction takes place in this region. The appearance of rate-maximum is explained on the basis of two effects associated in the pseudo-phase ion exchange model with ionic interchange. The addition of TTAB increases the relative concentration of substrate and OH^- in the Stern layer, leading to an increase in the reaction rate. When the surfactant concentration increases, Br^- ions added to the medium. These are non-reactive counterions. They compete with OH^- ions in the Stern layer thereby inhibiting the reaction. The relative contribution of these two associated factors give rise to the rate-maximum.

Conductivity measurements for CMC: The critical micelle concentration both in the absence (CMC) and in the presence of β -CD (CMC_{app}) have been determined from conductometric measurements at room temperature (27°). When a cyclodextrin/surfactant/water ternary system is studied, two processes (micellization and inclusion) should be considered⁹. The specific conductances were determined as a function of $[\beta\text{-CD}]$ at various concentrations of TTAB and SDS. The concentration of β -CD was constant (8.81×10^{-3} and 13.2×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³). The inflection observed in all plots between specific conductivity and surfactant concentration (Fig. not shown) at certain concentrations of TTAB and SDS, is considered to be the CMC of the micelles in the presence of β -CD, known as the apparent critical micelle concentration (CMC_{app}). Table 4 reports the values of CMC_{app} obtained. The CMC_{app} values of the SDS and TTAB increase with β -CD concentration from the CMC of the pure surfactant. The association between the β -CD and the surfactant is strong compared with the formation of micelles.

Table 4. Values of apparent CMC of TTAB and SDS at constant $[\beta\text{-CD}]$

$10^3 [\beta\text{-CD}]$ mol dm ⁻³	CMC_{app}	
	$10^3 [\text{SDS}]$ mol dm ⁻³	$10^3 [\text{TTAB}]$ mol dm ⁻³
0.00	8.60	3.60
8.81	13.7	9.20
13.2	17.0	11.7

Experimental

The SDS, TTAB, β -cyclodextrin and acetohydroxamic acid (Sigma) were used as such. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade. Triple-distilled water was used throughout. Kinetic procedures were basically the same as reported ear-

lier¹⁰. Conductance measurements were made at 27° using a Systronics 304 conductivity meter.

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